

How to include environmental sustainability criteria in national AI funding schemes?

Reflecting on the example of France and the Green Algorithms tool

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Artificial intelligence (AI) is in the media spotlight for its potential to transform the economic and research sectors, among others. This drives funding bodies to support AI-based innovation, with for example the Horizon Europe and Digital Europe programmes run by the European Union, or France's investment strategy France 2030 (national strategy for AI). On the other hand, the environmental impacts of AI are now better understood, and we cannot ignore the role of AI on electricity and water usage, mineral resource depletion, and greenhouse gas emissions^{1,2}. **To bring together innovation and sustainability, the French Department for the Environment (*Ministère en charge de la Transition Écologique*) has decided to require the use of the [Green Algorithms](#) tool for funding applications on the topic of AI and climate change. Applicants now have to include estimates of the carbon footprint and energy usage of the different development phases of the proposed AI solution.** This was tested on a first funding call "Demonstrators of frugal AI for sustainable development of local communities". The first applications were received in December 2023, with positive feedback from the different stakeholders. Applicants in particular approved of this new criterion, as they understood its necessity, found the tool easy to use, and did not consider this to slow down innovation. Following this successful implementation in a first funding call, it was decided to include the Green Algorithms tool more systematically in the application guidelines of other AI-related funding calls run by the Department. The goal of this piece is to reflect on the inclusion of environmental criteria in AI funding calls and share the lessons learned with other funding bodies internationally to promote similar initiatives across the AI ecosystem.

1. Why include environmental criteria?

AI is increasingly being used to tackle the climate emergency³, which prompted the French Department for the Environment to open a funding call in 2022 to support the deployment of AI solutions for sustainability in local communities (e.g. transports, energy efficiency of public buildings, water management, risk prevention etc.). To ensure that the solutions proposed resulted in a net benefit to the environment, it rapidly became clear that the environmental impacts of the AI models themselves had to be considered.

Concerns about the environmental impacts of AI are not new^{4,5} but heightened in recent years with the large-scale deployment of Large Language Models popularised by ChatGPT¹. The carbon footprint of these models reaches hundreds of tonnes of CO₂e (550 tonnes alone to train GPT-3 once, ChatGPT's precursor²). For context, the IPCC target is 2 tonnes of CO₂e per person and per year. **In light of the impacts of greenhouse gases on climate change and human health, it is legitimate to wonder to what extent AI projects are compatible with the DNSH principle (Do No Significant Harm) that all research projects have to follow according to Article 17 of the [European regulation on sustainable investment](#).**

Applicants to *France 2030* programmes were already required to self-assess the expected environmental impacts of their proposals – and compare it to the existing technology – according to 6 criteria (climate change reduction, climate change adaptation, sustainable use and protection of aquatic and marine resources, prevention and reduction of air pollution, protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems). This analysis is expected to include life cycle assessments of the project's outputs and methods. **In practice, applicants sometimes lack the tools to quantify these impacts, in particular in the digital sector.**

To be consistent, and to ensure that the digital projects funded do not disproportionately impact the environment, the Department has included more specific environmental criteria targeted at the AI system itself, as well as a quantification methodology to facilitate monitoring and comparisons. **The goal is to quantify ahead of time, and justify, the environmental impacts of the different stages of research and deployment of the proposed algorithms.**

2. Initial consultation about the criteria

For a successful integration, environmental criteria had to be both ambitious and user-friendly. **The environmental**

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impacts considered had to be specific and relevant while being straightforward to estimate so that applicants could take ownership of the environmental sustainability of their projects. One of the challenges was to find a way to estimate the carbon footprint of an AI solution before the start of the project, without existing code or known infrastructure needs.

Several tools have been released in the past few years to estimate the carbon footprint of high-performance computing and AI. These can be grouped according to three main categories: online calculators (e.g. similar to flight carbon calculators), softwares (packages) integrated into the code and tracking a computer’s energy usage, and energy dashboards offered by data centre providers. Only online calculators are adapted to estimate a carbon footprint before a project starts. They also have the added benefits of being user-friendly and installation-free. A literature review conducted by the Department led to the choice of **Green Algorithms**⁶, a free and open-source online tool. Independent studies confirmed the robustness of its methodology and the accuracy of the estimates obtained with it⁷. With this tool (Figure 1), applicants have to input the expected runtime, hardware used (CPU and/or GPU, memory), energy efficiency of the data centre and its location. All these parameters are already known, at least roughly, to the applicants who use them in the project’s budget. Based on this information, the tool estimates the total energy needed and the corresponding carbon footprint.

The calculator has been initially tested with previous applicants and internal project leaders in the Department. They confirmed the simplicity of using it in this context and for AI projects more broadly. This opened the way to its inclusion in the second round of the funding call **“Demonstrators of frugal AI for sustainable development of local communities”**.

3. Guidelines for applicants

The application guidelines require applicants to include a screenshot of the filled-in Green Algorithms calculator, as well as specifying the location of the computing infrastructures used for training and inference:

“The goal is to self-assess the predictable impacts of the proposed project (supported by France 2030) in line with a reference framework including a cost-benefit analysis balancing the negative impacts resulting from the unavoidable usage of resources (minerals, energy) with the environmental benefits of the project. [...] Furthermore, the application should specify the methodology used to estimate these impacts. The quantification of the carbon footprint of training the AI model must use the Green Algorithms tool as well as specifying the location of the servers.”

- Translated from the application guidelines.

In addition to the application guidelines, a webinar was organised to present the tool and answer any questions applicants may have.

Figure 1: Screenshot of the Green Algorithms online calculator (calculator.green-algorithms.org)

4. Using environmental criteria when assessing funding applications

A panel of experts assesses the applications through ten criteria, one of them being “Frugality of the AI models”, graded from 1 to 5. In this frugality criterion, the quality of the environmental impact estimation was assessed, as well as the proportionality between the expected carbon footprint and the project proposed. The quality assessment of the indicated energy consumption and carbon footprint enables the panel to ensure that the applicant has thoroughly considered the environmental sustainability component of their project from its early stages. At this stage, there isn’t a hard threshold applied to the environmental impact estimates deciding what should or should not be funded.

Progressive and mindful implementation of these metrics is essential for wide adoption.

Nonetheless, no project was accepted for this funding call without an environmental impact statement based on Green Algorithms. This was well-received by applicants; they complied and **were then quizzed about their impact assessment at the interview stage. Knowing that this is not only a tick-boxing exercise, but that they would have to defend their environmental impact statement at the interviews encouraged applicants to write more thoughtful statements.** Overall, all candidates proved that sustainability was part of design choices throughout the proposal.

5. Positive outcomes, lessons for future funding calls and systematic inclusion of environmental impact statements

This first experiment in a national funding call provided a wealth of information: these sustainability criteria are well received by the different stakeholders, who understand the need for them, and are useful indicators for reviewing panels and the Department. Applicants particularly appreciated that a specific tool (Green Algorithms) was listed in the application guidelines, as it streamlined the process while being easy to use and providing clear results.

Crucially, these criteria are not only descriptive but also promote sustainable project designs. Including them in funding applications guarantees that the environmental impacts of a project are considered before its start, rather than only retrospectively. This encourages sustainable planning, which goes beyond impact assessment. For example, an application to the call discussed above chose to reuse GPU servers rather than purchasing new ones and another limited the number of new sensors deployed for data collection. Such choices could be highlighted in the application through the environmental impacts statement, even though they weren't directly quantified in the calculator, and this was positively viewed by the panel.

This experiment also highlighted some aspects of the process in need of improvement, in particular to address inconsistencies between different applications' assessments and the lack of explanations provided. The different stages of AI projects were considered unevenly between projects, pointing to a need for more specific guidelines. Estimates provided sometimes lacked justifications which required the programme managers to follow up with applicants (the split between training and inference stages was a particular issue). The timeframe to consider was also not specified which made it difficult to compare different projects, especially the ones including continuous inference. This indicates that for these projects, it would be more suitable to report electricity usage and carbon footprint per month for example, rather than a total value.

Overall, these limitations are relatively easy to address and this first experiment has been a success. This led the Department to expand the inclusion of these criteria and the use of the Green Algorithms tool to other AI-related funding calls, fine-tuning the

guidelines to tackle the issues mentioned above. More recently, this has been implemented in [a funding call for Generative AI projects](#), with the following instructions included in the application guidelines.

“When using the Green Algorithms tool, it is essential to quantify two indicators for the proposed projects, energy consumption and carbon footprint. These should be reported for the two main phases of development:

- *The training phase, including research and testing as well as training of the full model (intermediary models, hyperparameter searches, all experiments and debugging, validation etc.). If relying on pre-trained models, the training cost of the pre-trained models is outside the scope of this estimate, provided that you can justify that this pre-trained model is widely used by the community. Furthermore, in situations where the final model is re-trained regularly during the production phase, both indicators (energy and carbon footprint) should be estimated on a per-month basis as well.*
- *The inference phase. For projects including a continuous inference phase (e.g. a chatbot interacting regularly with users), energy usage and carbon footprint should be estimated on a per month basis. If the inference phase only happens once (e.g. predictions are made once and the results made available), the indicators should be calculated for the entire phase.*

In both cases, an average estimate as well as an upper limit should be provided. Since these are estimates made before the project starts, assumptions can be made provided they are explained. Building estimates based on similar previous models can be a useful way to improve them.

Results should be given in kg CO₂e for carbon footprints and kWh for energy consumption. Training and inference phases should be clearly identified with separate indicators.”

- Translated from the application guidelines.

6. Long-term lessons: standards and data for sustainable AI projects.

To go even further, the French Department for the Environment published in June 2024 a [methodological framework for the environmental impacts of AI](#) which includes collaboratively agreed estimation methods and best practices. Ultimately, this framework will include best practices for sustainable public procurement of AI systems as well as sustainability criteria for AI-related public contracts.

One of the main limitations highlighted by this work is the lack of data on server manufacturing and usage, particularly regarding water and rare metals consumption. Such data is essential to conduct multi-impact analyses which go beyond greenhouse gas emissions only.

This experiment by the French Department for the Environment makes it clear that including specific and reliable sustainability criteria is both needed and

possible. The AI community dealing with them is ready to comply and tools such as Green Algorithms are able to inform reviewing panels on the sustainability of different projects. Sensible use of these criteria is crucial to their success, which doesn't prevent them from being considered seriously by the different stakeholders. Shared novel data and methods will feed into available tools such as Green Algorithms to expand environmental impact assessments and facilitate comparisons between projects.

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